

EFFECT OF TRANSVERSE STITCHING ON THE STRENGTH OF ADHESIVE BONDED COMPOSITE LAP JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

The effect of transverse stitching on the strength of composite lap joints is investigated using adhesive sandwich model with nonlinear adhesive properties for single lap and double lap joints. Numerical results indicate that, amongst all stitching parameters, pretension plays an important role in reducing peel stresses while increase in other parameters generally lead to small reduction in peel stresses. It is also shown that the stitching is likely to be effective for the joints where peel stresses are critical and ineffective for those where shear stresses are critical.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesively bonded composite lap joints find many applications in aerospace structures. It has been observed that adherend delamination in the ply adjacent to the adhesive is a typical form of failure for adhesively bonded composite joints due to weakness of the laminate in through-the-thickness direction [1,2]. Many investigators [3,4] have shown that through-the-thickness reinforcement in the form of transverse stitching improves both Mode I and Mode II delamination toughness of laminated composites significantly. However, little effort has been directed towards the study of stitching on the strength of composite lap joints. Tada and Ishikawa [5] evaluated the effects of stitching on CFRP laminates using a variety of specimens and tests, eg single lap joints in tension, plate with angle joints in peel loading, T-section stiffener in compressive loading, step lap joint in four point bending, and a plate with a hole in compressive loading. On the basis of their test results, they confirmed that transverse stitching is capable of resisting damage growth, arresting crack propagation and deferring final fracture.

In this study, a numerical analysis is presented to investigate the effect of stitching on the stresses and strengths of single- and double-lap joints. It is assumed that the joint is stitched through all the adherends. The force in the stitches is estimated from the elastic stretching of the thread and is separated into two components: (1) the transverse (or z) component which contributes to the peel stress in the adhesive and (2) the longitudinal (or x) component which contributes to the shear stress in the adhesive. The analysis allows arbitrary non-linear stress-strain behaviour for

the adhesive in both shear and peel. The formulation results in non-linear governing differential equations even when the adhesive is assumed to behave linear elastically and, therefore, numerical integration using shooting-to-a-point technique in conjunction with Newton-Raphson method is performed to solve these equations. The effect of stitches in reducing the peel and shear stresses in the adhesive is discussed for a variety of cases. Increase in pretension, stitch density, thread stiffness and stitch thread diameter generally leads to larger improvement in the strength of the joints.

ADHESIVE SANDWICH MODEL

An adhesive sandwich model [6] consists of an adhesive layer and two adherends and can be used to model the behaviour of the joint overlap. In this model, the adhesive layer is assumed to exhibit constant (through thickness) shear and peel strains created by the relative deformations of the two adherends. The adherends are assumed to behave like a beam that can undergo both longitudinal and lateral deflections or longitudinal deflection only. It is also assumed that the adhesive layer exhibits arbitrary nonlinear stress-strain behaviour in both shear and peel.

When considering a stitched adhesive sandwich model, the stitching thread is assumed to be stitched through the total thickness of the joint overlap. The deformed shapes of both double- and single-lap joints are depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Deformed double-lap and single-lap joints with transverse stitching

For a double lap joint, the adhesive sandwich model contains an outer adherend, half of the inner adherend, and the adhesive with nonlinear adhesive properties. Due to symmetry, it is assumed that, while the outer adherend has longitudinal and lateral displacements, the inner adherend only undergoes longitudinal displacement. When incorporating the contribution of stitching into both peel and shear stress, the seven first-order differential equations used by Tong et al. [7] are modified as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_{1,x} &= y_3 / A_1, & y_{2,x} &= A_o^* (P - y_3) / 2 + B_o^* y_7 \\
 y_{3,x} &= -2 \tau^*(\gamma), & y_{4,x} &= y_5 \\
 y_{5,x} &= -B_o^* (P - y_3) / 2 - D_o^* y_7, & y_{6,x} &= \sigma^*(\epsilon) \\
 y_{7,x} &= y_6 - \tau^*(\gamma) t_o / 2
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where y_1 and y_2 are the longitudinal displacements of the inner and outer adherends, y_3 is the membrane force of the inner adherend, y_4 , y_5 , y_6 and y_7 are the lateral deflection, slope of the lateral deflection, transverse shear force and bending moment of the outer adherend. The compliances of the outer adherends are $A_o^* = D_o / \Delta$, $B_o^* = -B_o / \Delta$, $D_o^* = A_o / \Delta$ and

$\Delta = A_o D_o - B_o^2$. The adhesive thickness is denoted by t . The shear and peel strains and stresses are given by

$$\gamma = \frac{y_2 - y_1}{t} + \frac{t_o}{2t} y_5, \quad \epsilon = \frac{y_4}{t} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau^*(\gamma) = \tau(\gamma) + \tau_s(\gamma) \quad \sigma^*(\epsilon) = \sigma(\epsilon) + \sigma_s(\epsilon) \quad (3)$$

where $\tau(\gamma)$ and $\sigma(\epsilon)$ are the adhesive shear and peel stress-strain curves measured using thick adherend lap shear specimen or napkin ring shear specimen and neat adhesive tensile test or butt joint test specimen, respectively. $\tau_s(\gamma)$ and $\sigma_s(\epsilon)$ are the shear and peel stress contributions from the force in the stitches and will be discussed in the next section.

For a single-lap joint, the adhesive sandwich model contains two adherends and an adhesive layer with nonlinear adhesive properties. It is assumed that both adherends have longitudinal and lateral displacements. When incorporating the contribution of stitching into both peel and shear, the governing equations can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{1,x} &= A_1^* y_2 + B_1^* y_6, & y_{2,x} &= -\tau^*(\gamma), & y_{3,x} &= y_4 \\ y_{4,x} &= -B_1^* y_2 - D_1^* y_6, & y_{5,x} &= -\sigma^*(\epsilon), & y_{6,x} &= y_5 - \frac{t_1}{2} \tau^*(\gamma) \\ y_{7,x} &= A_2^* y_8 + B_2^* y_{12}, & y_{8,x} &= \tau^*(\gamma), & y_{9,x} &= y_{10} \\ y_{10,x} &= -B_2^* y_8 - D_2^* y_{12}, & y_{11,x} &= \sigma^*(\epsilon), & y_{12,x} &= y_{11} - \frac{t_2}{2} \tau^*(\gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where y_i ($i=1,2,\dots,6$) and y_i ($i=7,8,\dots,12$) are the longitudinal displacement, membrane force, lateral deflection, bending rotation, transverse shear force and bending moment of the top and bottom adherend, respectively. The compliances of the top (denoted with subscript 1) and bottom (denoted with subscript 2) adherends are $A_i^* = D_i / \Delta_i$, $B_i^* = -B_i / \Delta_i$, $D_i^* = A_i / \Delta_i$ and $\Delta_i = A_i D_i - B_i^2$ ($i=1,2$). The adhesive shear and peel strains and stresses are given by

$$\gamma = \frac{y_7 - y_1}{t} + \frac{1}{2t} (t_1 y_4 + t_2 y_{10}), \quad \epsilon = \frac{y_9 - y_3}{t} \quad (5)$$

$$\tau^*(\gamma) = \tau(\gamma) + \tau_s(\gamma), \quad \sigma^*(\epsilon) = \sigma(\epsilon) + \sigma_s(\epsilon) \quad (6)$$

where, similar to Eqns (3), $\tau(\gamma)$ and $\sigma(\epsilon)$ are the adhesive shear and peel stress-strain curves. $\tau_s(\gamma)$ and $\sigma_s(\epsilon)$ are the shear and peel stress contributions from the force in the stitches.

STITCHING MODEL

As discussed above, the force carried by the stitching thread during the deformation of a joint reduces the stresses in the adhesive. In the absence of the stitching thread, this additional force would have been carried by the adhesive. In order to determine the contribution to the peel and shear stresses in the adhesive from the stitch thread, consider a single stitch thread embedded in a matrix with embedded length H as shown in Figure 2. The embedded end of the thread is assumed to be rigidly fixed to simulate the actual stitch behaviour where the thread only stretches and does not pull-out. During the initial elastic stretching of the thread, length Y is the portion of the thread carrying the load and is referred to as the slip length. As the load F carried by the thread increases, the slip length increases from 0 to H provided that the thread does not rupture. This process is called the activation of frictional slip. Since the embedded end remains intact, with further

increase in load F , both the displacement δ (which is related to the deformation of the joint) and the load at the embedded end increase. Any pretension F_t in the thread is assumed to remain constant along the whole length of the embedded thread. The force-displacement relationships for the stitch thread are given in Ref. [3]. These relationships, for most practical purposes, can be simplified as follows by expanding the logarithmic terms.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F &= \pi d_f \sqrt{\frac{2H\delta}{r} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} + F_t \quad \text{for } \sqrt{\frac{2H\delta}{r} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} \leq H \\
 F &= \pi d_f H + \frac{A_f E_f}{H} \left(\delta \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right) - \frac{Hr}{2} \right) + F_t \quad \text{for } \sqrt{\frac{2H\delta}{r} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} > H
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where r is the extensibility ratio, defined as $r = \pi d_f H / (A_f E_f)$, and A_f and E_f are the cross sectional area and the Young's modulus of the stitching thread, respectively.

In the case of a stitched joint, the stitch thread stretches from both the top and the bottom (middle in the case of a double lap joint) adherends as the load carried by the joint increases. The loading process of the thread can be divided into three stages: (1) activation of frictional slip in both the adherends, (2) continuation of frictional slip activation in the adherend with longer embedded length while the slip length has reached the embedded end in the other adherend, and (3) elastic stretching of the thread after the slip length has reached the embedded ends in both the adherends. The longer embedded length is designated as H_1 and the shorter embedded length is designated as H_2 . The corresponding extensibility ratios are represented by r_1 and r_2 . The force-displacement relationships in the joint may then be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F &= \pi d_f \sqrt{\frac{H_2\delta}{r_2} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} + F_t \quad \text{for } \sqrt{\frac{H_2\delta}{r_2} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} \leq H_2 \\
 F &= \pi d_f \sqrt{\frac{2H_1\delta_1}{r_1} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} + F_t \quad \text{for } \sqrt{\frac{2H_1\delta_1}{r_1} \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} \leq H_1 \\
 F &= \pi d_f H_1 + \frac{A_f E_f}{H_1} \left[\delta_2 \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right) - \frac{H_1 r_1}{2} \right] + F_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_1 &= \left[\frac{3r_2 H_2}{2 \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} + \delta \right] - r_2 H_2 \left[\frac{2}{\left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)^2} + \frac{2\delta}{r_2 H_2 \left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 \delta_2 &= \frac{r_1 r_2}{r_1 + r_2} \left[\left(\frac{H_2 - H_1}{2} \right) \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{F_t}{A_f E_f}\right)} + \frac{\delta}{r_2} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

and displacement δ is related to the shear strain γ and peel strain ϵ as follows:

$$\delta = \left(\frac{\gamma^2}{2} + \varepsilon \right) t \quad (10)$$

Once the force-displacement relationship in the stitch thread is determined, the contribution to the peel and shear stress in the adhesive due to the thread is given by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_s &= F \left(1 - \frac{\gamma^2}{2} \right) \\ \tau_s &= F\gamma \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

These expressions are then utilised in the governing equilibrium equations and constitutive laws (equations 1-3 for single lap joint and equations 4-6 for double lap joint) to examine the effect of stitching on the strength of the joint.

Figure 2. Elastic stretching of a thread embedded in the matrix.

SOLUTION STRATEGY

The first-order nonlinear differential equations given in Eqns (1-3) or (4-6) form a boundary value problem that is solved using shooting-to-a-fitting-point method in conjunction with the Newton-Raphson method [8]. In this method, the solution to the equations is found by launching shoots from both side of the interval and trying to match at some intermediate point. The iteration procedure begins with initial guess of the variables and the problem is solved as an initial value problem using Runge-Kutta method, then a correction is made to the initial guess from the mismatch at the intermediate point and iteration continues until the mismatch is within the tolerance. The globally convergent method for nonlinear systems of equations is utilised in the solution procedure. This algorithm combines the rapid local convergence of Newton's method that guarantees convergence towards the solution at each iteration.

The two failure criteria used to predict the respective failure models are:

- Maximum stress or maximum strain criterion: The joint is assumed to fail when one of the maximum stress components in the joint exceeds its limit strength. There are different types of failure modes, for example, shear or peel failure in the adhesive or in resin-rich area of the surface ply, tensile failure in the adherends, etc.
- Interlaminar failure criterion: The interlaminar delamination is assumed to happen when $(\sigma_p/Z)^2 + (\tau_p/S)^2 \geq 1$, where Z and S are the interlaminar normal and shear strength of the laminate, σ_p and τ_p are the maximum peel and shear stresses. The left hand term is the interlaminar delamination failure index.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two numerical examples are presented in this study. One is for a stitched single-lap joint and the other is for a stitched double-lap joint. In all calculations, the material properties of each ply are assumed as: $E_1=127000$ MPa, $E_2=10000$ MPa, $G_{12}=60000$ MPa, $\nu_{12}=0.3$. The strength allowables are $Z=50$ MPa and $S=60$ MPa. The ply thickness is 0.13 mm. The thickness of adhesive layer is assumed to be 0.12 mm. For linear behaviour of the adhesive, it is assumed that $E_a=2600$ MPa and $G_a=842$ MPa, for nonlinear adhesive, the stress-strain curves used are depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Stress-strain curves for the adhesive used in this study (solid diamond for tension or peel, solid squares for shear)

Example 1. Stitched single-lap joint: The single-lap joint is assumed to be simply supported at the ends of the overlap, eg, the left end of the top adherend and right end of the bottom adherend. The overlap length is 10 mm. The stacking sequence for both adherends is (0,90,90,0)s. The longitudinal tensile load is assumed to be 250 N. The baseline stitching parameters used in this study are: stitching density is 0.08 stitches/mm², thread diameter is 0.2 mm, pitch length is 2.5 mm, Young's modulus of the thread is 120 GPa.

Figures 4 and 5 indicate the effect of pretension in the stitches on the peel and shear stresses in the adhesive layer. The effect on the adhesive behaviour is also shown in these two figures. The stitching parameters used are their baseline values with zero thread-matrix shear stress. It is clearly shown that pretension in the stitches has a significant effect in reducing the maximum peel stress which causes failure of the joint and has negligible effect on the maximum shear stress.

Figure 6a depicts the effect of the thread-matrix shear stress on the maximum shear and peel stresses in the joints. In this case, the thread-matrix shear stress changes from zero to 25 MPa while the pretension was held constant as 25 N and the baseline values were used for all other stitching parameters. Evidently, the thread-matrix shear stress only has a slight influence on the peel stress when compared to the effect of thread pretension.

Figure 6b reveals the effect of the stitch density on the maximum shear and peel stresses in the joints. In the calculations, the stitch density ranges from 0.04 to 0.12 stitches per square mm while the pretension was held constant as 25 N, the thread-matrix shear stress remained as 5 MPa and all other stitching parameters take the baseline values. It is observed that the maximum peel stress is reduced with increase in stitch density. Although the effect of stitch density in reducing peel stresses in adhesive seems stronger than that of the thread-matrix interfacial shear stress, it is still less significant than that of pretension in the stitch.

Numerical results show that the thread diameter, Young's modulus of the thread and pitch length have negligible effect on the maximum shear and peel stresses in the adhesive layer. Hence it may be concluded from the present numerical example that among the six stitching parameters,

pretension has the most significant effect in reducing peel stress while the stitch density has a noticeable effect.

Figure 4. Effect of thread pretension on maximum peel and shear stresses in adhesive for stitched single-lap joints (solid diamonds for shear, solid squares for peel, solid lines for linear, dashed lines for nonlinear)

Figure 5. Peel and shear stress distribution along the overlap for the stitched single-lap joints with different pretension F_t in stitches, eg $F_t = 0$ denoted by solid squares, $F_t = 25$ N by solid triangles and $F_t = 50$ N by solid diamonds.

Figure 6. Effect of thread-matrix shear stress and stitch density on maximum peel and shear stresses in adhesive for stitched single-lap joints (solid diamonds for shear, solid squares for peel, solid lines for linear, dashed lines for nonlinear)

Example 2. Stitched double-lap joints. The double-lap joint is subjected to a longitudinal tensile load of 250 N. The overlap length is 10 mm. The stacking sequence for the outer and inner adherends are (0,90,90,0)s and (0,90,90,0)zs, respectively. In this case, linear adhesive properties

were used. The pretension was changed from zero to 15 N and the thread-matrix shear stress was set to zero, while the baseline values were input for all other stitching parameters. Table 1 gives the maximum shear and peel stresses as well as the minimum peel stress for the double-lap joints. It is noted that the pretension has a significant effect in reducing the positive peel stress and a negligible effect on the shear stress and the negative peel stress.

Table 1. Effect of pretension on maximum shear and peel stresses and on minimum peel stress in stitched double-lap joints

Pretension F _i	Max shear stress	Max peel stress	Min peel stress
0.0	22.0	15.5	-15.5
5.0	22.0	13.5	-15.4
10.0	22.0	11.8	-15.2
15.0	21.9	10.2	-15.5

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of stitching on the strength of composite double lap and single lap joints is investigated in this study. Using the adhesive sandwich models and the stitching model, it is found that the stitches have a significant effect on the strength of the joints where peel stress is critical and have no effect where shear stress is critical. Amongst all stitching parameters such as stitch density, thread stiffness and stitch thread diameter, pretension is the most important one in reducing the peel stress in the adhesive and thus improving the strength of the joints. For a double lap joint, stitches reduce the positive peel stresses and do not change the negative peel stresses. Hence stitches have a positive effect in improving the strength of the joint. For a single lap joint, the peel stresses are mostly positive and stitches always have a positive effect.

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